

Software user feedback survey, Requirements Engineering Journal Submission – Resource

Paper title: *Voice of the Users: An Extended Study of Software Feedback Engagement*

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Intro

前言

Hello and welcome!

你好，欢迎你！

Thank you for your willingness to participate in our survey. The goal of this research project is to better understand software users and the feedback they give about their software experiences. More details of the study can be found in the participant information sheet (PIS) available at [PIS](#). If you do not wish to take part in this survey, or if you do not agree with the conditions stated in the PIS, you may leave this survey by closing this window.

非常感谢你愿意参与到我们的调查中。这项研究项目的目标是更好地了解软件使用者和他们给出的关于软件使用体验的反馈。

这项研究的更多细节可以在参加者信息表（PIS）中找到，链接 [PIS](#)。如果你不想参加这项调查，或者是你不同意参加者信息表中阐述的条件，你可以关闭这个窗口来离开这项调查。

By clicking on "Next" you agree to the following:

通过点击“下一步”表明你同意下面列出的：

"I am 16 years of age or older. I have read and understood the information describing the aims and content of this project. I understand that by submitting this survey electronically, I agree to participate in the project under the terms detailed in the supplied PIS." 我同意根据所提供的参加者信息表中详细的条款参加这个项目。”

Approved by the University Of Auckland Human Participants Ethics Committee on 2 August 2017 for three years. Reference Number 019726.

奥克兰大学伦理审查委员会于 2017 年 8 月 2 日批准，为期三年。文献编号 019726.

End of Block: Welcome message

Start of Block: Default Question Block

Mobile Apps

手机应用程序

The google play store and apple app store, allow phone owners to download **mobile apps** onto their smart phones.

谷歌应用商店和苹果应用商店允许手机使用者把**手机应用程序**下载到自己的手机上。

Some popular **mobile apps** include Facebook, Twitter, Candy Crush WhatsApp and Viber.

一些流行的**手机应用程序**包括微信，微博，王者荣耀，绝地求生，腾讯视频等

Mobile apps often request a **star rating** and/or **written review** while you are using the app.

You can also go directly to the **app store** and give reviews.

当你在使用手机应用的时候，**应用程序**经常会要求**星级评分**和/或**写评价**。

你也可以直接去**应用商店**里面给出评价。

Q1 Please rate your agreement level with the following statements:

问题 1 请根据说明选择你的赞同程度

In the past, when a **mobile app** didn't meet my expectations, I've chosen **not** to write a review on the **app store** because,

过去，当一个**手机应用**没有满足我的期望的时候，我选择不在**应用商店**里写评论因为，

	Strongly Disagree 完全不同意	Disagree 不同意	Neutral 既不反对也不赞同	Agree 同意	Strongly Agree 非常同意
<p>I wasn't aware I could influence app improvements by writing an app store review 我没有想到我可以通过写一篇应用商店的评价来影响这个应用的改进</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>I thought it would take too long to get a resolution with an app store review 我认为通过应用商店的评价来解决这个问题需要很长时间</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>I've found the app store confusing or hard to use 我觉得应用商店令人迷惑或很难使用</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
<p>I didn't think an app store review would be seen by software producers or</p>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

lead to a resolution

我不认为软件开发者会看到应用商店的评论或找到解决方法

I would look for an existing answer online instead of writing an app store review

我会在网上寻找已有的答案，而不是在应用商店里写评价

I would look for an alternative app instead of writing an app store review

我会寻找一个替代的应用，而不是在应用商店里写评价

I didn't think my review would influence other app users

我不认为我的评价会影响到其他的应用用户

Other (please specify)

其他（请详细说明）

Support Forums

软件论坛

On **software support forums**, people hold conversations in the form of posted messages.

在**软件论坛**上，人们以发布消息的形式进行对话。

These **support forums** are used to discuss and support software/websites on

Windows/Mac/Linux computers.

这些**论坛**用于讨论支持 **Windows/Mac/Linux 计算机**上的软件/网站。

在论坛上，人们交换关于如何使用这个软件的经验或者问题。

(Support forum example)

(软件论坛举例)

Microsoft Word, Youtube (Website) and Fornite (multiplayer game) all use **support forums**.

如百度经验，百度贴吧等，此外，Microsoft Word、某些视频网站和一些大型游戏都使用**论坛**。

Q2 Please rate your agreement level with the following statements:

问题 2 请根据说明选择你的赞同程度

In the past, when software didn't meet my expectations, I've chosen not to post on a **software support forum** because,

过去，当软件没有达到我的期望时，我选择不在**软件论坛**上写帖子因为，

	Strongly Disagree 完全不同意	Disagree 不同意	Neutral 既不反对也不同意	Agree 同意	Strongly Agree 非常同意
I wasn't aware I could influence software improvements by posting on a support forum 我没有想到通过在软件论坛上写帖子可以影响软件的改进	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I thought it would take too long to get a resolution by posting on a support forum 我认为通过软件论坛的帖子来解决这个问题需要很长时间	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I've found support forums confusing or hard to use 我觉得软件论坛令人迷惑或很难使用	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I didn't think a support forum post would be seen by	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

software
producers or
lead to a
resolution

我不认为软件
开发者会看到
软件论坛的帖
子或找到解决
方法

I would look
for an existing
answer

instead of
writing my
own post on a
support forum

我会寻找已有
的答案，而不
是在软件论坛
上发帖

I would look
for an
alternative
software
product
instead of

posting on a
support forum

我会寻找替代
的软件产品，
而不是在软件
论坛上发帖

I didn't think
my forum
post would
influence
other
software
users

我不认为我的
论坛帖子能够
影响其他的软
件使用者

Other (please
specify)

其他（请详细
说明）

Q3 Please rate your agreement level with the following statements:

问题 3 请根据说明选择你的赞同程度

In the past, when software (or an app) didn't meet my expectations, I've chosen not to post on **social media** because,

过去，当软件（或应用）没有满足我的期望时，我选择不**在社交媒体**上写帖子因为，

	Strongly Disagree 完全不同意	Disagree 不同意	Neutral 既不反对也不赞同	Agree 同意	Strongly Agree 非常同意
I wasn't aware I could influence software improvements by posting on social media 我没有想到通过在社交媒体上写帖子可以影响软件的改进	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I thought it would take too long to get a resolution with a social media post 我认为通过社交媒体的帖子来解决这个问题需要很长时间	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I've found social media confusing or hard to use 我觉得社交媒体令人迷惑或很难使用	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I didn't think a social media post would be seen by software producers or	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

lead to a resolution

我不认为软件开发者会看到社交媒体的帖子或找到解决方法

I would look for an existing answer online instead of posting on social media
我会寻找已有的答案，而不是在社交媒体上发帖

I would look for alternative software (or app) instead of posting on social media
我会寻找替代的软件产品（或应用），而不是在社交媒体发帖

I didn't think my social media post would influence other software users

我不认为我的社交媒体帖子能够影响其他的软件使用者

Other (please specify)
其他（请详细说明）

Q4 Please rate your agreement level with the following statements:

问题 4 请根据说明选择你的赞同程度

I would be more likely to post on **app stores, forums** or **social media** about software issues or requests in the future if,

未来，我会更可能在**应用商店，论坛或者社交媒体**上发关于软件问题或要求的帖子如果，

	Strongly Disagree 完全不同意	Disagree 不同意	Neutral 既不反对也不赞同	Agree 同意	Strongly Agree 非常同意
I would receive a small financial incentive 我收到小额的金钱激励	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I would receive in app rewards. E.g. game currency, access to new features 我收到应用程序的奖励如：游戏货币，获得新功能	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could give feedback via audio 我可以通过音频方式给予反馈	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could give feedback via video 我可以通过视频方式给予反馈	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
I could give app feedback through a smart	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

assistant
(Alexa,
Google
Assistant,
Siri)

我可以通过智
能助手给应用
程序反馈（华
为语音助手，
谷歌助手，
Siri 等）

Other (please
specify)

其他（请详细
说明）

Q5 What type of computer do you currently use?

问题 5 你现在使用哪种型号的电脑?

(choose all that apply)

(选择所有符合的)

- Windows
 - Windows 操作系统
 - Mac (Apple)
 - Mac (苹果电脑)
 - Linux
 - Linux 操作系统
 - I don't use a computer
 - 我不使用电脑
 - Other (please specify)
 - 其他 (请详细说明)
-
-

Q6 What type of mobile phone do you currently use?

问题 6 你现在使用哪种型号的手机?

(choose all that apply)

(选择所有符合的)

- iPhone
 - 苹果手机
 - Android (Samsung, Google, etc)
 - 安卓手机 (三星, 华为等)
 - I don't use a mobile phone
 - 我不用手机
 - Other (please specify)
 - 其他 (请详细说明)
-
-

Q7 How many hours per day do you use your phone?

问题 7 你每天使用手机多长时间?

- Less than 1 hour
 - 少于 1 小时
 - 1 - 4 hours
 - 1-4 小时
 - 4 - 8 hours
 - 4-8 小时
 - More than 8 hours
 - 多于 8 小时
-

Q8 How many hours per day do you use your computer?

问题 8 你每天使用电脑多长时间?

- Less than 1 hour
 - 少于 1 小时
 - 1 - 4 hours
 - 1-4 小时
 - 4 - 8 hours
 - 4-8 小时
 - More than 8 hours
 - 多于 8 小时
-

Q9 Do you work or have you previously worked in the software industry?

问题 9 你现在或曾经在软件行业工作过吗？

(choose all that apply)

(选择所有符合的)

No

没有

I work or have worked **professionally** in software

我现在或曾经**专职**工作过

I have volunteered for an open source project

我自愿参加过一个开源项目

Other (please specify)

其他（请详细说明）

Q10 How **old** are you?

问题 10 你的**年龄**是?

Under 18 years old

小于 18 岁

18 - 24 years old

18-24 岁

25 - 34 years old

25-34 岁

35 - 44 years old

35-44 岁

45 - 54 years old

45-54 岁

Over 55 years old

大于 55 岁

Q11 What is your **gender**?

问题 11 你的**性别**是?

- Man
 - 男性
 - Woman
 - 女性
 - Gender diverse / Non-binary
 - 多样性别/非二元性别
 - Prefer not to say
 - 不想回答
 - Prefer to self-specify (please specify)
 - 想要自行指定 (请详细说明)
-
-

Q12 What is your **ethnicity**?

问题 12 你的**种族**是?

White/Pakeha (European)

白种人 (欧洲人)

Asian

亚洲人

Pacific/Maori people

太平洋/毛里人

African

非洲人

Middle Eastern

中东

Latin America

拉丁美洲

Other (please specify)

其他 (请详细说明) _____

Q13 What is your highest level of **education** completed?

问题 13 你的最高学历是?

- Secondary school - *E.g. High school (Abitur)*
 - 高中
 - Post secondary, Vocational training - *E.g Electrician, Police Officer, Real Estate Agent*
 - 大专
 - 1-2 year tertiary education - *E.g Undergraduate Certificate or Diploma*
 - 本科毕业
 - Bachelor degree (3-4 years)
 - 本科学历
 - Masters degree (postgraduate)
 - 研究生学历
 - Doctoral degree (postgraduate)
 - 博士学历
 - Other (please specify)
 - 其他（请详细说明） _____
-

Q14 What is your current **employment** status?

问题 14 你现在的**就业**状态是？

- Employed full-time (40+ hours a week)
- 全职（每周 40+小时）
- Employed part time (Less than 40 hours a week)
- 兼职（每周少于 40 小时）
- Currently unemployed
- 无业
- Student
- 学生
- Retired
- 退休
- Self-employed
- 个体经营
- Unable to work
- 不能工作
- Other (please specify)
- 其他（请详细说明）_____